

Competence Approach in Modern Engineering Education of Ukraine: Assessment of Development

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Introduction

Framework for Qualifications of the European Higher Education Area and European Framework for Qualifications for Lifelong Learning, EU education regulations, have a number of differences from the Ukrainian National Framework of Qualifications and Ukrainian Higher Education Standards (HES).

Ukraine declares its desire for European integration, its desire to participate in the Bologna process, but it standardizes its legislation on education too slowly and inconsistently.

МІНІСТЕРСТВО
ОСВІТИ І НАУКИ
УКРАЇНИ

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НАУКА

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МІНІСТЕРСТВО

ПРЕСЦЕНТР

ЗАТВЕРДЖЕНІ СТАНДАРТИ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ

Спеціальність	Рівень освіти	Дата та номер наказу	Рік набрання чинності
141 Електроенергетика, електротехніка та електромеханіка	бакалавр	20.06.2019 р. № 867	2019/2020
142 Енергетичне машинобудування	бакалавр	19.10.2018 р. № 1136	2018/2019
142 Енергетичне машинобудування	магістр	16.04.2021 р. № 427	2021/2022
143 Атомна енергетика	бакалавр	10.07.2019 р. № 964	2019/2020

Aim of the study

to optimize the requirements for the list and content of competencies in modern engineering higher education of Ukraine in accordance with the national and European qualification frameworks.

Results

In all HES of Ukraine, without exception, "integral competence" is described as "the ability to be a specialist" in one's specialty, that is, in fact, it is redundant.

The list of general and professional competencies is too large.

Names of competences are too long, they consist not of one word, but of whole sentences.

The content of the same competence in different HES is described in different ways.

HES not describes the competence level that a Bachelor's, Master's, and Philosophy Doctor's should achieve.

The list of key competences of the Law of Ukraine "On education" differs from the list of key competences of the European Union.

Competences in HES of Ukraine, key competences of Ukraine and key competences of the European Union are not correspondence.

NATIONAL QUALIFICATIONS FRAMEWORK OF UKRAINE

Approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine № 1341, dated November 23, 2011,
as amended by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine № 519, dated June 25, 2020

Conclusions

The list of competencies that a graduate should master should be shortened.

The names of competencies should be shortened to one word (digital, mathematical, drawing, etc.)

The designations of these competencies should be included into the Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education".

HES must determine the levels of formation of each of the competencies.

Thank you for your attention!